

Mapping Collaboration and Core Journals in Doctoral Research: A Bibliometric Study of Library and Information Science, Manipur University (1990–2018)

Moirangthem Lokendro Singh

Research Scholar, DLIS, and Assistant Librarian, Manipur University, Canchipur

Email: mls.res.2023@gmail.com & al@manipuruniv.ac.in

Dr. Bobby Phuritsabam

Associate Professor, DLIS, Manipur University, Canchipur

Email: bobbyphster@gmail.com

Received: 21-08-2025

Revised: 24-08-2025

Accepted: 25-08-2025

Abstract: *The study examines 31 doctoral theses awarded by the Department of Library and Information Science, Manipur University, between 1990 and 2018. It uses non-source data extracted from the bibliographies or references appended at the end of each thesis. These data (bibliographic entries) are imported into Excel using KIMI and analyzed in Microsoft Excel, Jamovi (Version 2.6.26) and Bradford's Laws to meet the study's objectives. Three thousand nine hundred twenty-two (3922) bibliographic references appended to these theses were extracted and analysed. The study aims (i) to identify authorship collaborations using various indicators for measures of collaboration such as Degree of Collaboration (DC), Collaboration Index (CI), and Collaboration Coefficient (CC); (ii) to find out the prioritized medium used for exchanging research communication and (iii) to sort out the core journals of the respective studies. The findings suggest that more authors collaborating for research, intensifying collaborative networks, and enriching the university library's journal subscriptions will enhance research productivity and scholarly communication.*

Keywords: Bibliometrics, Doctoral Research, Authorship Collaboration, Core Journals, Manipur University, Bradford's Law, Research Productivity

1 Introduction

Research offered in a higher educational institution is an avenue for knowledge generation and dissemination. Scholarly communication paves the way for the progressive nature of the research.

Bibliometric methods enable the mapping of authorship and citation trends, and the identification of the types of most preferred documents used. Research collaboration amongst the authors, in particular, helps to boost research productivity, interdisciplinarity and scholarly impact. Similarly, the identification of core journals ensures that libraries subscribe to the resources and informs academic researchers about the most influential sources in their disciplines.

The present study focuses on doctoral theses from the Department of Library and Information Science, a constituent department of Manipur University established in 1986. Since the Library and Information Science has produced doctoral research in library and related social science fields, no bibliometric study has previously analysed its citation, sources and authorship trends. This paper seeks to fill that gap by examining theses produced between 1990 and 2018.

2 Literature Review

Research collaboration assessment using bibliometric indicators is not a new concept anymore. Various pioneers have studied and established mathematical formulas to highlight the shift from single-authored to multi-authored research in most disciplines. First and foremost, Subramanyam (1983) introduced the Degree of Collaboration, followed by subsequent refinements such as the Collaboration Index (Lawani, 1980), and the Collaboration Coefficient (Ajiferuke et al., 1988).

In their study, Bozeman et al. (2013) explore thoroughly how university researchers work together among themselves and with people in business or other fields. It also underlines how these partnerships can aim to widen horizons or foster prosperity through academic entrepreneurship. The authors classify the key elements that influence how collaborations happen and what impacts they have. In addition, they have shared practical aspects on how collaborative research can improve, like focusing on motives, measuring real impacts, and addressing issues like exploitation.

Bruneel et al. (2010) illuminate that previous collaborative experience fosters trust and reduces barriers to future collaborations, facilitating more successful outcomes. Similarly, having a history of alliances can engender the trust necessary for effective partnership.

Diamond (1985) elaborated from the study of Berkeley Mathematicians that citations to multi-author papers are worth more to authors in terms of their earning ability or salary than citations to single-author papers.

Katz and Martin (1997) highlighted that people collaborate at the most basic level, not institutions. Direct co-operation between two or more researchers is the fundamental unit of collaboration. Certain factors pushed the researchers to work together like – high cost involved in the scientific instrumentation; affordable cost of travel and accessibility with the introduction of fax machines and electronic mail; interactions with other scientist with the development of invisible colleges or the network; increasing need of specialization within certain scientific fields especially those where the instrumentation required is very complex; growing importance of interdisciplinary research; and healthy political relations influences greater level of collaboration among the researcher. He further mentioned that for decades, the multi-author publication, frequently referred to as a co-authored publication, has been used as a basic counting unit to measure collaboration activity.

Lee and Bozeman (2005), in their paper ‘The Impact of Research Collaboration on Scientific Productivity’ explained that modern science research has become more interdisciplinary, complex, and

costly in nature, encouraging scientists to get involved in collaborative research. Funding agencies, particularly government agencies, facilitate active research collaboration as part of their funding conditions.

Lawani (1986), in his study of cancer research, highlighted that, as the number of authors per paper increases, the proportion of high-impact papers also increases.

Nilsson et al. (2010) emphasise that a supportive infrastructure within the universities enhances researchers' confidence in engaging industry partners, while informal interactions between scientists and private sector actors can trigger more formal collaborations.

Nudelman & Landers (1972) mentioned that the scientific community has given more weight to all the authors of a jointly authored paper than to the author of a single-author paper.

Ponomariov and Boardman (2008) note that informal interactions between scientists and private sector actors can lead to more intense collaborations, and

Price and Beaver (1966) in their study found that the rate of productivity increased as the number of collaborators increased.

Rubinandhini & Gomathi (2015) conducted an authorship analysis of the journal *Annals of Library and Information Studies* and detected the values of CC and DC 0.38 and 0.67, respectively. Authorship collaboration is an intense form of research interaction that allows for effective communication as well as the sharing of competence and other resources among or between researchers or scientists (Melin & Persson, 1996).

Siamaki et al. (2014) in their study in *Library & Information Science Studies in Iran* found that the values of Degree of Collaboration (DC), Collaboration Index (CI), and Collaborative Co-Efficiency (CC) were 0.46, 1.58, and 0.23, respectively, which shows moderate collaboration among the authors.

Smith (1958) examined 4189 papers from *American Psychologist* published between 1946 and 1957 and concluded that the mean number of authors per paper increased from 1.3 to 1.7. Price (1963) mentioned that since the beginning of the 20th Century, the proportion of multiple-authored papers has accelerated at a much faster rate and predicted that if the same trend continues, by 1980, there would be no single-authored paper.

Subramanyam (1983) states that collaboration in research occurs through sharing data, advice, or an idea through correspondence or at conferences, visiting each other's research facilities, or performing parts of a project separately and then integrating the results. He further mentioned in his studies that scientists extensively used prior information to adopt a reliable framework to study scientific knowledge's generation, processing, and communication. One of the accepted norms widely followed is the established practice of giving credit to earlier records of science when the information contained in them is used in a subsequent investigation. He adopted six (6) types of collaborations: Teacher-pupil collaboration; Collaboration among colleagues; Supervisor-assistant collaboration; Research Consultant Collaboration; Collaboration between Organizations; and International Collaboration.

Several studies, such as Pandey & Sahoo (2020); Waghmode, et.al. (2020), demonstrated a very high degree of authorship collaboration.

The study includes identification of the core journals used by scholars of the library science disciplines, Manipur University. Bradford's Law of Scattering, one of the three bibliometric laws, formulated in

1934 by Samuel C. Bradford, is used to identify the core journals on a specific subject using the number of journals, articles or citations as the basic parameters. The law states that if journals are arranged in order of decreasing productivity on a given subject, they can be divided into three zones [such as First Zone (core or nucleus), Second Zone, and Third Zone] where each zone contains an equal number of articles. However, the number of journals in each zone increases geometrically. Thus, this paper aims to assess research collaboration, identify the most preferred research medium and core journals out of the cited resources used by the scholars.

3 Objectives

The study aims to:

- 3.1 Investigate authorship collaboration patterns using bibliometric indicators.
- 3.2 Distinguish the preferred media of research communication in doctoral research.
- 3.3 Confirm Bradford's Law to determine the core journals cited in doctoral theses.

4 Methodology

The study is based on 3,922 citations data extracted from 31 doctoral theses awarded at Library and Information Science from 1990 to 2018. These data are non-source bibliographical data compiled from the appendices of these theses.

4.1 Data Collection: The pdf files of the bibliographic data uploaded into google drive and extract the OCR enable text in word file. The data thus extracted are arranged and imported into Microsoft Excel using KIMI (Knowledge & Information Management Interface).

4.2 Data Analysis: Statistical analysis was carried out in Excel and Jamovi (Version 2.6.26). Indicators such as DC, CI, and CC were applied to measure research collaboration trends using MS Excel, and the most preferred document types and testing of Bradford's Law for identification of core journals, dividing the dataset into productivity zones using Jamovi Software.

5 Results and Discussion

5.1 Authorship Collaboration:

Mathematical representation for calculating different bibliometric indicators to measure research collaboration are shown below as:

5.1.(a) Degree of Collaboration (DC) formulated by Subramanyam K (1983) is used to measure the proportion of multi-authored papers out of the total published works within a given dataset.

Formula:

$$\text{Degree of Collaboration (DC)} = N_m / N_m + N_s$$

Where N_m = Number of Multi-author paper

N_s = Number of Single-author paper

Interpretations:

- If the value of DC=0, it means all publications are single-authored papers.
- If the value of DC=1, it means all publications are multi-authored papers.
- The value of DC ranges from 0 to 1, a higher value in DC implies a greater tendency toward collaboration in research.
- It does not distinguish the size of collaborative groups.

5.1. (b) Collaboration Index (CI) was formulated by Lawani M in 1980, which is used to compute the mean number of authors per paper of scholarly content focusing more on the intensity of the collaboration within a specific time period.

Formula for CI:

$$CI = [\sum_{j=1}^A (j * f_j)] / N$$

Where:

j= the number of authors on a paper.

f_j= the number of papers with 'j' authors.

N= the total number of papers published.

\sum = (sigma) indicates the summation of all papers, from the minimum number of authors to the maximum.

Interpretations:

- The value of CI is greater than equal to 1
- The value of CI gives a useful sense of the scale of collaboration (more authors per paper on average)
- The value of CI always gives a mean value rather than a proportion.

5.1. (c) Collaboration Coefficient (CC) was formulated by Ajiferuke in 1988 which is applicable to measure of the degree of collaboration in research, often applied to authorship patterns in scientific publications. In simple sense, it measures the probability of multi-authored papers in a dataset. It accounts for the different levels of multiple authorships, not just the presence or absence of collaboration, by giving more weight to papers with higher numbers of authors.

The formula for the collaboration coefficient (CC) is:

$$CC = 1 - \sum [(1/j) * (f_j)] / N$$

Where:

j= the number of authors on a paper.

f_j= the number of papers with 'j' authors.

N= the total number of papers published.

\sum = all possible values of j (number of authors), up to the maximum number of authors found in a single paper.

Interpretations:

- CC values range from 0 to 1.
- If the value of CC=0, All the papers are single-authored papers.
- If the value of CC is closer to 1, the chance of co-authored papers increases in the dataset which reflects a higher collaborative intensity within the research community.
- The CC was developed to address limitations of other measures like the Collaboration Index (CI) and the Degree of Collaboration (DC), providing a more nuanced measure of collaboration.
- The value of cc does not reach to 1 unless infinite authors.

Results obtained from the extracted compilation of 3922 citations with different bibliometric indicators values are shown in Table 1 below:

Table 1 shows multi-authorship patterns along with calculated values of DC, CI and CC

LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SCIENCE THESES (31) _MU_1990_2018 Citations for all Sources															
Sl.No.	Period	Multi-Author							Nm	Total AC(Ns+Nm)	Unknown author(s)	Grand Total	DC	CI	CC
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7							
1	Prior-1947	54	7						7	61		61	0.11	1.11	0.06
2	1948-1957	37	4						4	41		41	0.10	1.10	0.05
3	1958-1967	140	12			1			13	153		153	0.08	1.11	0.04
4	1968-1977	330	62	3		6			71	401		401	0.18	1.23	0.09
5	1978-1987	561	108	4		25			137	698	3	701	0.20	1.31	0.11
6	1988-1997	490	94	6	1	12			113	603		603	0.19	1.26	0.10
7	1998-2007	866	351	60	10	28	2	2	453	1319	1	1320	0.34	1.48	0.19
8	2008-2017	267	178	66	7	8		1	260	527		527	0.49	1.70	0.28
9	Unknown Date									115		115			
										3918	4	3922			
Average Citations per Thesis		127 Citations/Thesis													

5.1.(a) The finding of the study demonstrates that the Degree of Collaboration (DC) value is found to be (i) highest during the year 2008-2017 with 0.49, and (ii) lowest during the year 1958 to 1967 with a value of 0.08. The DC Values range from 0 to 1. From the data obtained from the present study, it can be interpreted that the lower the value of DC, the majority of the research done was single-authored and weak collaboration; on the other hand, higher DC values show multi-authored and strong collaboration. Derivatives from the present dataset reflect a transition from individualistic research to more collaborative research and the growth of a research environment where research scholars became aware of the benefits of collaborative work.

5.1.(b) The study reveals that the Collaboration Index (CI) value is found to be (i) highest during the year 2008-2017 with 1.70, and (ii) lowest during the year 1948 to 1957 with a value of 1.10. The CI values are normally greater than or equal to 1. From the data obtained from the present study, it can be interpreted that the lower the value of CI, the majority of the research was done in solo mode or minimal collaboration; on the other hand, higher CI values show shifting towards multi-authored and stronger collaborative authorship and demonstrate a new positive evolution of the collaborative research ecosystem.

5.1.(c) From the present dataset, it is found that the CC values (0.04–0.28) indicate that the research output was initially dominated by single-authored works, reflecting weak collaborative research. In the later stages, the Collaboration Coefficient increased nearly sevenfold, indicating increased

collaborative research uptakes. Although research collaboration is still in the infant stage, the upward trajectory demonstrates a positive trend toward joint research activity, signalling a shift from solo research to cooperative research practices.

The present study found values of the **Degree of Collaboration (DC)** ranged from **0.08 to 0.49**, the **Collaboration Index (CI)** ranged from **1.10 to 1.70**, and the **Collaboration Coefficient (CC)** ranged between **0.04 and 0.28**, together providing a comprehensive outline of authorship collaboration in the research output studied. Initially, the research work done by the scholar consulted works done solo or independently. The research output has gradually shown an increase in incorporating more collaborative or teamwork, seeing the benefits of collaboration in terms of progressive and collective gains. Thus, the three indicators reveal a **consistent upward trend in research collaboration**.

5.2 Medium of Communication

Various media of scholarly communication were found used in the research publications. Among them, journals are the most frequently cited source, followed by books, conference proceedings, book chapters, website resources, newspaper articles, theses and dissertations, government publication reports, etc. This study aligns with global social science research trends, where journals serve as the primary knowledge exchange medium. Details shown in Table 2

Table 2 demonstrates the most preferred document types cited by the scholars

Frequencies	
Type of Document Cited	Count
Journal Articles	1855
Book	939
Conference Publications	488
Book Chapter	224
Website	107
Newspaper Article	89
Thesis	59
Government Publications	51
Report	47
Dissertation	19
Printed Manipuri Puya	10
Unpublished Documents	8
Annual Report	7
Magazine Article	5
Government Publications	4

Frequencies	
Type of Document Cited	Count
Speech	3
Newsletter	2
Records	2
Annual Report	1
Letter To The Editor	1
Working Paper	1
	3922

Figure-1 shows the most preferred document types cited in Chart

5.3 Core Journals

The application of Bradford's Law distinguishes a consolidated set of journals constituting the 'core' of doctoral research in Library and Information Science. These journals, consistently cited across multiple theses, represent foundational sources for management research. Their delineation provides strategic guidance for collection development within the University Library, ensuring maximised access to high-impact scholarly resources.

(a) Bradford's Law of Scattering is applied to identify the core or nucleus journals mostly cited by the research scholars of management disciplines.

Formula:

The number of the journals in each zone are given in the following ratio:

$$1: n: n^2$$

where “n” is the Bradford’s Multiplier.

Bradford Multiplier represented by ‘n’ is calculated as mean value of Zone2/Zone1:Zone3/Zone2

Application of Bradford’s Law of Scattering in the current study

The dataset consists of 1855 Journal articles out of the 3922 various resources, constituting 47.30%. The frequency of the journal citations in the dataset is extracted using Jamovi software (version 2.6.26), which also ranks journals. One thousand eight hundred fifty-five (1855) journal articles are published in 527 Journal Titles. In the process, for identification of core journals in the dataset, bibliometric measures such as Bradford's Law of Scattering and Leimkuhler Model are used to test the validity of the possibilities based on the data

Table 3 shows scattered articles cited in Journals

Bradford's Law of Scattering applied to the Cited Journals				
Zone	No. of Journals	No. of Citations	% of Citations	Bradford Multiplier (n)
1	11	615	33.15	
2	49	621	33.48	4.45
3	467	619	33.37	9.53
Total	527	1855	100	6.99

Table 3 shows zone-wise journals and distributed articles or citations. First (Core or Nucleus) Zone consists of 11 journals, Second Zone with 49 Journals, and Third Zone with 467 Journals. The mean value of Bradford's Multiplier is n=6.99

Mathematically,

Identified Zones are arranged in the geometrical series, $1: n: n^2$ - (1)

[Bradford’s Law of Scattering]

$$\% \text{ Error} = \frac{\text{Total Calculated Value of Journals} - \text{Total Given Value of Journals}}{\text{Total Given Value of Journals}} \times 100 \quad \text{-(2)}$$

In equation (1) above, Bradford’s Multiplier Value, n=6.99 is applied, [derived from Table 3 above]

$$\text{Then, } 1: n: n^2 :: 11: (11 \times 6.99): [11 \times (6.99)^2]$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Therefore, the total value of journals derived is} &= 11 + 76.89 + 537.4611 \\ &= 625.3511 \quad \text{-(3)} \end{aligned}$$

Putting the derived value of journals i.e. 625.3511 from (3) in equation (2),

$$\begin{aligned} \text{\% Error} &= \frac{625.3511-527}{527} \times 100 && [\text{Total Given Value of Journals} = 527] \\ &= 18.66\% \end{aligned}$$

Since the percentage (%) Error is quite high, the dataset does not fit into the Bradford's Law of Scattering.

(b) Leimkuhler Model & its applications:

The **Leimkuhler model**, introduced by Ferdinand F. Leimkuhler in 1967-68, is a mathematical formalization and generalization of Bradford's Law of Scattering. It provides a quantitative value for describing how articles or citations are distributed across journals or sources, often using geometric or analytic functions, especially in fields where a few sources cite maximum articles or citations while many others contribute much less.

Egghe (1990) introduced a new mathematical formula, which modifies Leimkuhler's model for calculating Bradford's multiplier 'k'. The proposed model is given below

$$k = (e_y \times Y_m)^{1/p} \quad - (4)$$

Where:

$e_y = 1.781$ (Euler's constant; sometimes represented as e^y in texts)

Y_m = number of articles (or citations) in the **most productive source** (i.e., the journal with the most articles in the dataset) = 114

p is the **number of Bradford zones** (groups that contain similar number of articles)

Using the value from the dataset,

$$\text{New Bradford's Multiplier 'k'} = (1.781 \times 114)^{1/3} \approx 5.88 \quad - (5)$$

Mathematically, the number of journals in the first (core or nucleus) zone of Bradford is calculated using the formula given below with new modifier:

$$\begin{aligned} r_0 &= \frac{T(k-1)}{(k^p-1)} && \text{where, T = Total Number of Journals} \\ &= \frac{527(5.88-1)}{(5.88^3-1)} \\ &= \frac{2571.76}{202.297472} && \approx 12.713 \quad - (6) \end{aligned}$$

Then the value in the subsequent new zones are calculated as given below:

$$r_1 = r_0 * k = 12.713 \times 5.88 = 74.75 \quad - (7)$$

$$r_2 = r_0 * k^2 = 12.713 \times (5.88)^2 = 12.713 \times 34.57 = 439.5 \quad - (8)$$

Now, putting the values of (5) (6), (7) and (8) in Bradford New Zone of Scattering

i.e. $r_0 : r_1 : r_2$

$$12.713 : 12.713 \times 5.88 : 12.713 \times (5.88)^2$$

$$12.713 : 74.75 : 439.5$$

Therefore, the value becomes = 526.96 -(9)

$$\text{Then, Percentage (\%) Error} = \frac{526.96 - 527}{527} \times 100$$

$$= \frac{-0.04}{527} \times 100 = -0.0076\%$$

Therefore, it is found that calculation the percentage error is very minimal which can be neglected.

Hence the Bradford's law of scattering fits very well in the present dataset for the New Bradford multiplier $k = 5.88$.

Newly derived Bradford's Zones are shown below:

Table 4 shows New Bradford's Zone Value Using New Modifier Value i.e. 5.88

New Bradford's Zone Using New Modifier Value for Cited Journals				
Zone	No. of Journals	No. of Citations	% of Citations	New Bradford Multiplier (k)
1	12.71	648	34.933	
2	74.75	687	37.035	5.881
3	439.50	520	28.032	5.879
Total	526.96	1855	100	5.88

(c) Based on the new zones, core journals from the dataset are shown below:

Table 5 provides the list of Core Journals preferred by the LIS, Scholars, MU

SI No	Source of Publications	No. of Articles or Citations	Cummulative Value
1	IASLIC Bulletin	114	114
2	ILA Bulletin	96	210
3	Reference Services Review	66	276
4	Library Review	49	325
5	Annals of Library Science and Documentation	46	371
6	Herald of Library Science	46	417
7	Journal of Documentation	45	462

SI No	Source of Publications	No. of Articles or Citations	Cummulative Value
8	New Library World	43	505
9	The Electronic Library	39	544
10	Indian Journal of Information, Library & Society	36	580
11	SRELS Journal of Information Management	35	615
12	Library Trends	33	648

Figure-2 shows graphical representation of 12 core journals, LIS, Manipur University

The study has identified the 12 core journals preferred by most scholars, with IASLIC Bulletin on the top followed by ILA Bulletin, Reference Services Review, Library Review, Annals of Library Science and Documentation, Herald of Library Science, Journal of Documentation, New Library World, The Electronic Library, Indian Journal of Information, Library and Society, SRELS Journal of Information Management and Library Trends.

6. Data Source:

The data used in analysis are accessible at URL: <http://bit.ly/4781jX4>.

7. Conclusion

The bibliometric study of awarded doctoral theses at Library and Information Science, Manipur University, demonstrates increasing trends in authorship collaboration, shown various preferred communication medium used and the primary role of journals in scholarly communication. The identification of core journals and the key preferred choice of types of documents for scholarly communication provides insight for library collection development and enhances better academic

services by aligning with the library's decision-making. The study contributes to the broader understanding of doctoral research citation practices and collaboration patterns. The study findings could be expanded to comparative analyses across departments and universities.

References:

- Bozeman, Barry, Fay, Daniel & P. Slade, Catherine (2013). Research collaboration in universities and academic entrepreneurship: the-state-of-the-art. *J Technol Transf*, 38, 1-67
- Bruneel, J., D'Este, P. & Salter, A. (2010). Investigating the factors that diminish the barriers to university–industry collaboration. *Research Policy*, 39(7), 858–868
- Diamond, A. M. (1985). The money value of citations to single-authored and multiple-authored articles. *Scientometrics*, 8(5–6), 315–320. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02016900>
- Egghe, L. & Rousseau, R. (1990). *Introduction to Informetrics: Quantitative methods in library, documentation and information science*. Elsevier Science Publishers.
- Katz, J. S., & Martin, B. R. (1997). What is research collaboration? *Research Policy*, 26(1), 1–18.
- Lawani, S. M. (1986). Some bibliometric correlates of quality in scientific research. *Scientometrics*, 9(1–2), 13–25.
- Lee, S., & Bozeman, B. (2005). The impact of research collaboration on scientific productivity. *Scientific Collaboration*, 35(5), 673–702. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/25046667>
- Melin, G., & Persson, O. (1996). Studying research collaboration using co-authorships. *Scientometrics*, 36(3), 363–377. <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf02129600>
- Nilsson, A. S., Rickne, A., & Bengtsson, L. (2010). Transfer of academic research: Uncovering the grey zone. *The Journal of Technology Transfer*, 35(6), 617-636
- Nudelman, A. E., & Landers, C. E. (1972). The failure of 100 divided by 3 to equal 33 1/3. *The American Sociologist*, 7(1), 9.
- Pandey, S., & Sahoo, S. (2020). Research collaboration and authorship pattern in the field of semantic digital libraries. *DESIDOC Journal of Library & Information Technology*, 40(6), 375–381. <https://doi.org/10.14429/djlit.40.06.15680>
- Ponomariov, B., & Boardman, P. C. (2008). The effect of informal industry contacts on the time university scientists allocate to collaborative research with industry. *The Journal of Technology Transfer*, 33(3), 301–313
- Price, D. J. de S. (1963). *Little science, big science*. Columbia University Press.
- Price, D. J. de S., & Beaver, D. de B. (1966). Collaboration in an invisible college. *American Psychologist*, 21(11), 1011–1018.
- Rubinandhini, A., & Gomathi, P. (2015). Authorship pattern on Annals of Library and Information Studies output during 2005–2014: A bibliometric study. *International Journal of Engineering Science & Management Research*, 2(9), 141–150. Retrieved from <http://d1wqtxts1xzle7.cloudfront.net/14-libre.pdf>

- Siamaki, S., Geraei, E., & Zare-Farashbandi, F. (2014). A study on scientific collaboration and co-authorship patterns in library and information science studies in Iran between 2005 and 2009. *Journal of Education and Health Promotion*, 3(1). <https://doi.org/10.4103/2277-9531.139681>
- Simte, T. P., & Phuritsabam, B. (2022). Identifying authorship collaboration patterns and applying Bradford's law of scattering in the Department of Library and Information Science. In P. Babbar, P. K. Jain, B. Markscheffel, D. C. Kar, & R. Sangchantr (Eds.), *Metrics, indicators, mapping and data visualizations in webometrics, informetrics and scientometrics* (pp. 218–226). B.K. Books International.
- Smith, M. (1958). The trend toward multiple authorship in psychology. *American Psychologist*, 13(10), 596–599.
- Subramanyam, K. (1983). Bibliometric studies of research collaboration: A review. *Journal of Information Science*, 6(1), 33–38.
- Viju, W., & Ganesh, V. (2013). Application of Bradford's law of scattering to the literature of library & information science: A study of doctoral theses citations submitted to the universities of Maharashtra, India. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 1. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2569&context=libphilprac>
- Waghmode, S. S., Lathkar, R. A., & Kulkarni, J. N. (2020). Research publication trends in Indian LIS journals: A scientometric study. *Library Philosophy and Practice*. <http://eprints.rclis.org/40437/>

Websites:

Manipur University. (2025). Manipur University. <https://www.manipuruniv.ac.in>

INFLIBNET Centre. (2025). Shodhganga: A reservoir of Indian theses. <https://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in>